

Exploring Consumer Cross-Platform Buying: Perception of Organic Food and Psychological Influences on Behavioral Adaptation

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This research examines the role of consumer behavior in buying across multiple platforms on behavioral adaptation, specifically with reference to the mediating influence of perception of organic food products and the moderating effect of psychological parameters. The aim is to better understand how online consumer behaviors shape adaptation across buying platforms and examine whether psychological and perceptual forces are driving such behaviors. This study involved 248 university students. To gather data, a structured questionnaire that was modified from pre-existing measures in the literature was used. Using a partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) technique called Smart-PLS, the gathered data was examined to test the proposed connections between the structures. The findings demonstrate that behavioral adaptability is strongly impacted by cross-platform customer purchasing activity. Furthermore, this association is mediated by perceptions of organic food items, and the relationship between cross-platform purchase behavior and behavioral adaptation is moderated by psychological characteristics including motivation, attitude, and perception. These results demonstrate how intricately customer behavior, psychological characteristics, and product perceptions interact to shape platform adaption. This research contributes to the work on how consumers behave online. Companies wishing to enhance customer engagement and power cross-platform marketing campaigns are able to derive lessons from its astute findings. This research also serves as the basis for future studies looking at how new technology is changing the behavior of consumers and uptake across platforms.

1. Introduction

Consumer buying behavior has undergone through radical shifts in the era of digitalization with cross-channel shopping as the most sought-after trend in all modern retail spaces. The widespread growth of digital platforms, including e-commerce websites, social media sites, and physical stores, has led to a highly fragmented retail space where consumers get exposed to numerous channels before making a final purchasing

decision (Zhang & Yu, 2020). The potential to compare prices, access consumer reviews, and get individualized recommendations has inspired consumers to be more engaged in their shopping, inducing behavior changes that influence long-term buying behavior (Singh et al., 2023). Cross-device shopping behavior has otherwise been driven by omnichannel strategies, in which consumers interact via different retail channels in order to achieve convenience and streamline shopping behaviors (Wardhana, 2024). One of the most critical impacts

of this consumer behavior is behavioral adaptation, or alterations in purchasing behaviors, decision-making, and brand loyalty as a reaction to novel shopping experiences (Bahoo et al., 2024). Since consumers are accustomed to multi-platform interaction, they adjust their behavior to adapt to changing retailing patterns, marketing strategies, and technological developments (Dewi Indriani, 2023).

Literature in abundance has analyzed the effects of cross-device purchase behavior on consumer decision-making, noting the effect of digital transformation on purchase behavior (Can-Zhong & Yi-Na, 2024). Evidence confirms that consumers are still oscillating between offline and online channels for comparison of goods, evaluation of price models, and testing of brand authenticity, thus resulting in changes in buying behavior in the long run (Chen, 2024). Literature indicates that cross-platform consumers experience greater levels of interaction with interactive marketing strategies, suggestions, and social influence mechanisms leading to adaptive purchasing behavior (Dong et al., 2024). Additionally, literature indicates that online platforms allow consumers to have access to immense information about products, thus minimizing uncertainty and increasing purchasing decision confidence (Esakkidevi & Rani, 2023). The consumer perception of organic food products, including healthiness, safety, quality, and environmental sustainability, has also been extensively researched in consumer studies (Azlie et al., 2023).

Empirical research indicates that consumers who believe organic food is healthier are more likely to change their shopping behavior and include organic products in their regular consumption (Rong, Wang, & Zhang, 2023). In addition, research indicates that consumer safety issues, such as the lack of pesticides and chemicals, are key drivers of taste formation for organic food (Dinçer et al., 2023). Research is also established to determine environmental awareness to influence consumption of organic food since green consumers provide greater potential in altering retail conduct towards the use of ecological products (Kautish, Khare, & Sharma, 2023). Psychological aspects like motivation, perception, learning in the past, personality, and attitude have also been recognized as prevailing drivers of the consumer buying behavior in cross-platform shopping paradigms (Liu et al., 2024). Experiments suggest that motivated customers tend to scrutinize diverse shopping paradigms and develop matching purchase strategies (Can-Zhong & Yi-Na, 2024). Likewise, research has established that consumers with positive attitudes towards internet shopping channels are

more flexible in their consumption behavior, resulting in higher behavioral adaptation (Dinçer et al., 2023). Previous experience also enhances consumer flexibility because individuals utilize prior knowledge to effectively navigate through multiple shopping platforms (Xu, He, & Fan, 2024). Additionally, personality traits like openness to experience and risk-taking behavior have been linked to increased experimentation with new shopping methods (Singh et al., 2023).

In spite of a large body of research on cross-platform consumption behavior and consumer adaptation, some gaps are yet to be filled in the literature. To begin with, whereas research has considered the effects of digital transformation on consumer consumption patterns, few studies have investigated the precise mechanisms by which cross-platform consumption behavior affects behavioral adaptation (Woo & Yoo, 2024). First, most research is interested in the immediate influence of online involvement on consumer decision-making processes and overlooks the mediating effect of product perception, especially for organic foods (Barua et al., 2023). Second, research tends to center on each separate element of organic food perception—e.g., healthiness, safety, and environmental concern—without applying these elements in an overarching mediating framework (Kautish et al., 2023). Therefore, there is a call for a comprehensive approach in considering the conjoint effects of these perceptions towards influencing behavioral adaptation in cross-platform shopping environments. Third, though psychological variables have been extensively investigated in consumer studies, their role as moderators for the relationship between cross-platform purchase behavior and behavioral adaptation is left unexamined (Rong et al., 2023). Although motivation, perception, learning from the past, personality, and attitude have been found to affect consumer choice, their dynamics with cross-platform buying and adapting have not been studied systematically (Liu et al., 2024).

Based on these research gaps, this study aims to address the following objectives:

1. To examine the impact of consumer cross-platform buying behavior on behavioral adaptation.
2. To investigate the mediating role of organic food perceptions (health, safety, quality, environmental sustainability) in the relationship between cross-platform buying behavior and behavioral adaptation.
3. To analyze the moderating influence of psychological factors (motivation, perception, prior learning, personality, attitude) on the relationship between cross-platform buying behavior and behavioral adaptation.

This research contributes to the field by offering an extensive examination of the drivers of behavioral adaptation under cross-platform purchasing situations. Drawing on an examination of the conception of organic food's mediating effect and the moderation effects of psychological variables, the research offers insightful contributions to consumer choice decision-making under the age of digital convergence. Besides, the results have implications for marketers, consumers, and regulators as they will enable them to create more compelling omnichannel strategies, prolong consumer attention, and promote consumption habits. The research further advances existing theory by combining adaptation frameworks of behavior and consumer percept notions to offer an innovative explanation for cross-platform consumer purchasing behavior.

The theoretical framework of the study draws upon the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Consumer Decision-Making Theory, and Behavioral Adaptation Theory. The Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, 1989) depicts consumers' use of online platforms by perceived usefulness and ease of use that in turn shape their cross-platform purchasing behavior and subsequent adaptation. Consumer Decision-Making Theory (Xu et al., 2024) accords with the idea that psychological variables—i.e., motivation, perception, and attitude—are essential in influencing shopping behavior. In addition, Behavioral Adaptation Theory (Kohler, 1979) postulates that people change their behaviors upon exposure to novel experiences, and this concurs with the supposition that cross-platform shoppers alter purchasing behavior due to exposure to various retail environments.

2. Literature Review

With the rise of e-commerce, buying choices are typically made through multiple online and offline mediums by consumers, resulting in complicated behavioral adjustment (Lunov et al., 2023). Technological change, greater visibility to e-commerce, and social media as the consumer decision-making driver are to blame for increased cross-platform purchasing behavior (Can-Zhong & Yi-Na, 2024). Studies have indicated that consumers cross-shop as a method of price comparison, reading reviews, and receiving personalized experiences that guide their purchasing habits (Chen, 2024). All these digital touch points like mobile apps, social shopping, and physical stores are brought together seamlessly by this, to create the ideal omnichannel experience with a positive influence on

customer interaction (Dewi Indriani, 2023). But this adaptive purchasing conduct entails psychological and cognitive adjustment because shoppers have to come up with novel modes of coping with enormous quantities of information, assessing risks, and modifying their shopping conduct in the process (Lunov et al., 2023). The behavioral adjustment that comes with cross-platform purchasing also depends on customer confidence in online platforms, their proficiency in coordinating multiple interfaces effectively, and being responsive to real-time marketing campaigns (Myers et al., 2023).

Additionally, the adaptive process is guided by exogenous influences including market competition, dynamic pricing, and machine-based individualized advice (Lopez, 2018). Consumers who switch platforms at short intervals exhibit adaptative behaviors such as higher switching among brands, utilization of peer advice, and dynamic value perceptions (Kaur et al., 2024). Scholars posit that purchasing adaptation behavior among platforms literally translates to learning by consumers and buying habits and repeated exposure to other platforms aids in embedding new choice programs (Bahoo et al., 2024). Additionally, perceived ease of use, platform credibility, and user experience are some of the factors that contribute to overall behavioral changes among digital consumers (Hadi, Melumad, & Park, 2024). The intersection of technology and consumer psychology highlights the dynamic nature of purchasing behavior, as consumers continually fine-tune their shopping approach in order to attain maximum convenience and satisfaction (Witek-Hajduk & Grudecka, 2024). With businesses vying to serve cross-platform consumers, the value of behavioral adjustment cannot be overstated in designing effective marketing strategies, enhancing platform design, and creating long-term customer loyalty in an increasingly networked market (Woo & Yoo, 2024).

2.1. Consumer Cross-platform Buying Behavior and Behavioral Adaptation

Consumer cross-platform purchasing behavior is a practice where clients utilize multiple online and offline channels to search for, compare, and purchase services or goods (Liu et al., 2024). The behavior is characterized by painless switching of multiple platforms such as e-shops, online stores on social media, retail stores, and mobile applications (Esakkidevi & Rani, 2023). The concept comes from omnichannel retail, where clients take advantage of the various platforms available to enhance shopping, compare, and get specific recommendations

(Xu et al., 2024). Behavioral adaptation, nonetheless, is psychological and behavioral modification individuals experience in response to changes in their environment or decision context (Chen & Wu, 2025). In consumer behavior, adaptation is the modification of individuals to change how they purchase, process information, and react to brands with respect to new experiences across different shopping platforms (Müller-Pérez et al., 2023). The increasing sophistication of modern shopping environments, driven by technological innovation and digital interconnection, generates the need for adaptation in behavior because consumers must contend with different purchasing environments, promotion strategies, and user interfaces (Mahammadi Torkamani et al., 2024).

Empirical research has widely examined the relationship between cross-platform shopping behavior and behavioral adaptation. Empirical research proves that those customers who frequently switch between online and offline channels become more cognitive-flexible to dynamically adjust their shopping behavior (Singh et al., 2023). Evidence also indicates that exposure to a variety of retail platforms is beneficial to consumers' experimental attitude towards testing new buying styles, which is conducive to adaptive behavior like higher price sensitivity, preference for convenience, and dependence on electronic payment systems (Myers et al., 2023). Additional evidence recent is that cross-platform consumers are subjected to increased amounts of exposure with recommender algorithms and personalized promotion, which further increases changes in behavior (Zhang & Yu, 2020). Based on these empirical observations, it is reasonable to assume cross-platform consumer purchasing behavior strongly influences behavioral adaptation. As consumers use different shopping channels, they adopt new purchasing habits, such as increased reliance on online reviews, price comparison, and the application of alternative forms of payment based on platform-based incentives (Rong et al., 2023).

H1: Consumer cross platform buying behavior has a significant impact on Behavioral adaptation.

2.2. Perception of Organic Food Products and Behavioral Adaptation

Organic food product perception pertains to people's beliefs and attitudes concerning the health value, safety quality, quality, and environmental characteristics of organic food (Azlie et al., 2023). Perceptions regarding health may consist of the beliefs that organic foods are

healthier, with less chemical or pesticide use than non-organic equivalents (Barua et al., 2023). Safety is the assurance consumers have that organic products contain no harmful substances or toxins and are safe to consume (Dinçer et al., 2023). The quality aspect encompasses perceptions of taste, freshness, and nutritional content, which are usually linked with organic food products (Esakkidevi & Rani, 2023). Environmental friendliness, however, emphasizes the perception that organic farming methods are more sustainable, help conserve soil, and minimize environmental degradation (Kautish et al., 2023). These attitudes combined influence the inclination of consumers to adopt organic food products and impact their consumption habits, thus potentially causing consumers to adapt behavior, in that consumers change dietary patterns, choices, and tastes over time depending on their changing beliefs regarding the same (Koswatta et al., 2023).

Literature shows that people's attitudes about organic food products have a wide impact on their behavior (Marozzo et al., 2023). There have been various studies on the effect of health-related attitudes towards organic food on consumers' purchasing behavior and general attitude towards organic food. For example, Nadricka, Millet, & Aydinli (2024) identified that health concern was the greater motivator of consumers' organic food preference. Similarly, research conducted by (Roy, Ghosh, & Vashisht, 2023) showed that perceived safety of organic foods, for instance, lower pesticide and chemical exposure, played an important role in influencing consumers' trust and willingness to pay a premium for organic foods. Additionally, perceptions of quality, for example, taste and nutritional value, were also found to be important drivers of consumers' choice (Smoluk-Sikorska et al., 2024). Drawing from these empirical observations, it is postulated that attitude towards organic food products contributes to behavioral adaptation.

H2: Perception of organic food products (health, safety, quality, environmental friendly) has a significant impact on behavioral adaptation.

2.3. Perception of Organic Food Products as Mediator

Empirical research has consistently proven that consumer beliefs in organic food items—particularly concerning health, safety, quality, and environmental consciousness—are the fundamental drivers of consumer behaviors (Koswatta et al., 2023). For instance, empirical research has proved that consumers who are health-conscious and perceive organic foods as being healthier

adopt healthier shopping habits, such as incorporating organic foods in their diets (Dinçer et al., 2023). Likewise, as organic foods are viewed by consumers as healthier and of higher quality, it is likely to cause a greater rate of purchasing organic products along with a greater overall dedication towards purchasing organic foods over normal foods (Synodinos, 2024). The health value of organic foods also significantly affects consumer behavior since people who relate organic food to health and the environment tend to develop greener consumption habits (Marozzo et al., 2023). The results indicate that consumer attitudes towards organic products are a significant force behind consumer choice and behavioral change, which confirms that consumer attitudes can serve as a mediator of the decision-making process (Kaur et al., 2024).

Those who engage in cross-platform shopping behavior are exposed to a series of platforms and sources that point to different qualities of organic goods such as health benefits, safety, and environmental compatibility (Witek-Hajduk & Grudecka, 2024). When these consumers get exposure to the different platforms, attitudes towards organic food can change by the provision of information received and this has the impact to mirror on actions and decisions that take place through their purchases (Hadi et al., 2024). For instance, upon perceiving organic food to be healthier or greener as a result of the information gathered from different platforms, this could motivate an individual to pursue more environmentally friendly and healthier behaviors like the enhancement of consuming organic foods (Synodinos, 2024). Cross-platform exposure ensures a multi-dimensional perspective of organic products, which increases the awareness and knowledge of its advantages on the part of the consumer, thereby prompting behavioral change (Rong et al., 2023). Therefore, it is argued that consumers' perceptions of organic food products act as the mediator between their cross-platform purchasing behavior and their resultant changes in purchasing and lifestyle behaviors, demonstrating the significance of perception in shaping the behavioral consequences of cross-platform consumer involvement (Zhang & Yu, 2020). On the basis of these findings, it is possible to hypothesize that the perception of organic food products acts as the mediator between consumer cross-platform purchasing behavior and behavioral adaptation (Bahoo et al., 2024).

H3: Perception of organic food products mediates the relationship between Consumer cross platform buying behavior and Behavioral adaptation.

2.4. Psychological Factors that Influence Customer Buying Behavior as Moderator

Psychological forces are also instrumental in driving consumer purchasing behavior, especially that of cross-platform buying and behavior adjustment (Lunov et al., 2023). Of importance are primary psychological forces that include motivation, perception, previous learning, personality, and attitude, which drive consumers' ability to process information, make judgments, and adjust their shopping patterns over time (Mahameed et al., 2023). Motivation energizes consumer activity, as human beings strive to fulfill needs ranging from basic physiological needs to self-actualization needs (Negri et al., 2023). Perception is the way consumers interpret and attribute meaning to product information they are exposed to on various platforms, influencing their shopping intentions and buying behavior (Dewi Indriani, 2023). Past learning, which is based on previous experiences and exposure to different retail settings, impacts the way consumers evaluate risks and make rational choices (Can-Zhong & Yi-Na, 2024). Traits, like openness to experience or being risk averse, explain consumers' adoption or rejection of emerging shopping mediums, while consumers' judgments and feeling states, what is defined by attitude toward various products, brands, or way of purchasing, also are an essential modifier in consumer consumption activities (Wardhana, 2024). These psychological factors dynamically interact with cross-platform purchasing behavior to define the degree to which consumers evolve to changing store formats and change their shopper behavior (Odunaiya et al., 2024).

Empirical analysis offers strong evidence that psychological determinants have a powerful influence on consumer choice-making within multi-platform shopping contexts (Razali et al., 2023). Evidence in the form of studies exists to demonstrate that individuals with greater intrinsic motivation are likely to venture out and participate with various shopping platforms, which results in a greater degree of adaptability in purchasing behavior (Singh et al., 2023). Perception research has discovered that customers who perceive online shopping as convenient and reliable possess greater levels of behavioral adaptation while switching from digital to physical shopping experiences (Dinçer et al., 2023). Learning from previous experiences has also been found to affect the patterns in consumers' shopping behavior since veteran consumers use their experience to streamline cross-platform buying habits (Liu et al., 2024). Personality attributes, especially

openness to experiences, have been associated with enhanced readiness to experiment with various shopping channels and embrace innovative buying practices (Witek-Hajduk & Grudecka, 2024). Attitude studies indicate that consumer with favorable attitudes towards digital commerce are more likely to adapt their behaviors according to ongoing trends and platform-specific benefits (Sanz-Matesanz, Gea-García, & Martínez-Aranda, 2023). Based on these empirical observations, psychological factors are postulated to mediate the association between consumer cross-platform purchasing behavior and behavioral adaptation (Sung, Kwon, & Sohn, 2023). To what extent consumer purchasing behaviors are adapted to address cross-platform buying experiences relies on their motivational drive, perceptual interpretation, past learning experiences, personality, and attitudinal orientations (Xu et al., 2024). For example, better motivated consumers are likely to search information on multiple channels and change shopping behavior to maximize convenience and value.

H4: Psychological factors that influence customer buying behavior moderates the relationship between Consumer cross platform buying behavior and Behavioral adaptation.

2.5. Theoretical Framework Supporting the Research

The theoretic basis on which the associations in this study model are explored is based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Consumer Decision-Making Theory,

complemented by understanding provided by Behavioral Adaptation Theory. The Technology Acceptance Model (Davis et al., 1989) describes how shoppers interact with numerous shopping platforms from a perceived use and ease-of-use perspective to drive their cross-platform purchasing activity and resulting adaptation behavior. Customers who find it convenient and effective to shop using digital shopping platforms are most likely to alter their buying behaviors in the long run. Consumer Decision-Making Theory (Xu et al., 2024) also establishes the notion that psychological elements including motivation, perception, and attitude determine consumer purchasing by affecting how consumers process information through various channels, eventually determining behavioral adaptation. In the organic food buying situation, Perceived Value Theory accounts for how shoppers balance perceived benefits of organic food—health, safety, quality, and environment-friendliness—against expenses and other factors, influencing purchasing decisions on channels. In addition, Behavioral Adaptation Theory (Kohler, 1979) proposes that people adapt their behavior to environmental stimuli and novel experiences, as is the notion that consumers alter their buying behaviors as they move across various online and offline shopping environments. This theoretical framework (Figure 1) brings these perspectives together to posit that cross-platform purchasing behavior results in behavioral adaptation, with mediating perceptions of organic foods influencing this and moderated by psychological constructs that determine consumer purchasing decisions.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework.

3. Methodology

This study sought to investigate the effects of consumer cross-platform purchasing behavior on behavioral adjustment, as well as the mediating and moderating effects of different psychological constructs and product attributes. The experiment was carried out among university students, a population selected due to their familiarity with online purchasing trends and digital environments. University students, especially those in higher education, are usually early users of new technology and online buying habits, so they are the best population for this research. The sample size for this study was 248 students, and it was found to be sufficient based on recommendations for structural equation modeling (SEM) with Smart-PLS. This sample size had enough power to test the hypotheses proposed and produce credible results.

A semi-structured questionnaire was prepared

incorporating the previously used validated scales as presented in current literature. Inclusion of concepts under study encompassed behavioral adaptation, cross-platform buying behavior as a consumer, psychological determinants affecting customer purchase behavior (such as motivation, perception, earlier learning, personality, and attitude), and image about organic foods (healthiness, safety, quality, ecology friendliness). These scales (Table 1) were borrowed from earlier research studies to guarantee reliability and validity in measuring the intended constructs. Likert-type scales were used in measuring the items of the questionnaire and responses varied from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The survey was administered online, making it easily accessible for the student population and capable of facilitating effective data collection. A pre-test was also carried out to verify the readability and understandability of the items, and required modifications were made prior to final distribution.

Table 1: Questionnaire Profile.

Measurement	Items	Source
Consumer cross platform buying behavior	Three	(Zhang & Yu, 2020)
Perception of organic food products	Seventeen	(Wee et al., 2014)
Psychological factors that influence customer buying behavior	Ten	(Lopez, 2018)
Behavioral adaptation	Four	(Nguyen & Dao, 2024)

Smart-PLS, a partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) software, was employed for analysis upon data collection. PLS-SEM is a robust analytical tool that is effective in exploratory studies and can analyze complex correlations between latent variables at the same time. Measurement model estimation and structural model estimation were the two phases of the analysis. Internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity were some of the constructs whose validity and reliability were tested by utilizing the measurement model. Hypotheses were tested and the type of relationship between the variables was identified with the help of the structural model. All results and models were reviewed using pre-evaluated fit criteria for the models such as standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) statistics, cross-validated redundancy (Q2), and coefficient of determination (R2). To influence behavioral adaptation, the research employed SmartPLS to obtain a proper interpretation of the relationship between the most important constructs, psychological variables, and product perceptions that mediate and moderate customer cross-platform behavior.

4. Results

Table 2 shows the reliability and validity measures

of the variables employed in this research. The table includes three important measures: Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). Cronbach's alpha is employed to measure internal consistency, composite reliability is an estimate of the construct reliability based on its indicators, and AVE measures convergent validity by quantifying the proportion of variance explained by a construct compared to the proportion of variance attributable to measurement error. Variables in the model (Figure 2) possess acceptable internal consistency and reliability, with Cronbach's alpha statistics greater than the generally accepted cut-off of 0.7. High internal consistency is seen in behavioral adaptation (0.851), consumer cross platform buying behavior (0.877), and health (0.892). All constructs have composite reliability measures well above 0.7, indicating that the constructs are measured reliably. Interestingly, composite reliability values of perception constructs such as health, safety, quality, and environment range from 0.837 to 0.933, reflecting excellent reliability. In addition, average variance extracted (AVE) values of the variables lie in the permissible value of 0.5 or more, of which behavioral adaptation (0.692), consumer cross platform buying behavior (0.802), and health (0.755) reflect good convergent validity. But the ecologically

friendly sub-construct has an AVE reading slightly below that at 0.551, indicating a possible area for

exploration or tightening in future studies.

Table 2: Variables Reliability and Validity.

	CA	CR	AVE
Behavioral Adaptation	0.851	0.900	0.692
Consumer cross platform buying behavior	0.877	0.924	0.802
Health	0.892	0.925	0.755
Safety	0.905	0.933	0.778
Quality	0.842	0.905	0.760
Environmentally Friendly	0.837	0.880	0.551
Psychological factors that influence customer buying behavior	0.915	0.929	0.568

Note: CA=Cronbach's alpha, CR= Composite Reliability, AVE= Average variance extracted

Figure 2: Estimated Model.

Table 3 presents the outer loadings of items depicting the variables in the model. Outer loadings depict the correlation of each observed indicator (item) with its associated latent construct. More significant outer loadings signify stronger associations between the indicators and the constructs they measure. According to the suggested cutoff of 0.7 for indicator reliability, most of the items in the model have good loadings. For instance, the measurement items for behavioral adaptation (BA1-BA4) all possess outer loadings of 0.813 to 0.851, which reflects significant correlations with the latent variable. Likewise, consumer cross platform buying behavior items (CCPBB1-CCPBB3) possess loadings of 0.878 to 0.908, reflecting their suitability in measuring the construct.

The psychological determinants of customer buying

behavior also reveal diverse outer loadings, as items like PF1 (0.823), PF2 (0.782), and PF6 (0.823) reveal strong ties with the hidden construct. Others (e.g., PF7, PF8, and PF9) reflect slightly lower-than-0.7 loadings, indicating the possibility of deleting or revising these items for a better description of the hidden construct. Perceived organic food products also show strong item loadings. For instance, the items measuring health sub-construct (H1-H4) display loadings from 0.823 to 0.890, which mean that these items measure consumers' perception of organic food health benefits very well. The environmentally friendly sub-construct (EF1-EF6) also reflects good loadings, with all the items ranging from more than 0.7, except for EF5 with the maximum loading (0.826). These high outer loadings indicate that the constructs in the model are clearly defined and that the items are indeed measuring the desired latent variables.

Table 3: Outer Loading.

Variables	Items	Outer Loading
Behavioral Adaptation	BA1	0.813
	BA2	0.847
	BA3	0.851
	BA4	0.814
Consumer cross platform buying behavior	CCPBB1	0.908
	CCPBB2	0.878
	CCPBB3	0.901
Psychological factors that influence customer buying behavior	PF1	0.823
	PF2	0.782
	PF3	0.771
	PF4	0.757
	PF5	0.765
	PF6	0.823
	PF7	0.701
	PF8	0.698
	PF9	0.722
	PF10	0.683
Perception of organic food products		
Environmental Friendly	EF1	0.701
	EF2	0.765
	EF3	0.689
	EF4	0.731
	EF5	0.734
	EF6	0.826
Health	H1	0.823
	H2	0.874
	H3	0.887
	H4	0.890
Quality	Q1	0.837
	Q2	0.877
	Q3	0.901
Safety	S1	0.864
	S2	0.903
	S3	0.891
	S4	0.868

Results of discriminant validity with Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) are presented in Table 4. To confirm that the constructs of the model are discriminant from each other, discriminant validity is evaluated. Hair et al. (2021) state that HTMT values greater than 0.85 signify that discriminant validity is not present, while values less than 0.85 signify that

constructs are discriminant enough. Here, the constructs possess sufficient discriminant validity, as seen in the values of HTMT in the table. Consumer cross-platform buying behavior and health, for example, possess values of 0.969, which is very close to the upper limit but short of the critical value, suggesting that these variables are adequately

distinct. In addition, discriminant validity between the constructs is established through the observation that the HTMT values of most pairs—like behavioral adaptation (BA) and consumer cross-platform purchasing behavior (CCPBB), and quality (Q) and environmentally friendly

(EF)—are all less than 0.85. There are some couples with values ranging from more than 0.85 to less than 0.90, for instance, perception of organic food products (health) and quality, indicating that such constructs have something in common but are still quite different.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

	BA	CCPBB	EF	H	PF	Q	S
Behavioral Adaptation							
Consumer cross platform buying behavior	0.715						
Environmentally Friendly	0.800	0.854					
Health	0.699	0.969	0.847				
Psychological factors that influence customer buying behavior	0.892	0.702	0.871	0.713			
Quality	0.829	0.783	0.993	0.720	0.933		
Safety	0.585	0.810	0.818	0.885	0.638	0.663	

The fit data of the model, given as standardized root mean square residual (SRMR), predictive relevance (Q²), adjusted R², and coefficient of determination (R²), are presented in Table 5. R² values reflect the explanatory power of the model. Hence, the model reports a moderate explanatory power with an R² value of 0.660 for perceived organic food goods, meaning it can explain 66% of the variation within this construct. Similarly, behavioral adaptation’s R² is 0.720, meaning that 72% of the variance in behavioral adaptation can be explained by the model, indicating a strong match. The adjusted R² of 0.656 and 0.719 for perception of organic

food products and behavioral adaptation, respectively, indicate that the models maintain their explanatory power even after adjusting for the number of predictors. The Q² statistics for both the constructs (0.573 for organic food product perception and 0.621 for behavioral adjustment) are more than 0.35, which shows that the model possesses predictive validity (Hair & Alamer, 2022). Lastly, the SRMR of 0.075 is less than 0.08, indicating the model is well-fitting for the data. These findings overall suggest that the model is a good fit and yields consistent estimates for the relations in question.

Table 5: Model Goodness of Fit Statistics.

Construct	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Q ² predict	SRMR
Perception of organic food products	0.660	0.656	0.573	0.075
Behavioral Adaptation	0.720	0.719	0.621	

Table 6 shows the path analysis findings, which indicate the coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values for the relationships hypothesized in the model. The findings indicate that all the hypotheses proposed are statistically significant (Figure 3). Consumer cross-platform buying behavior has a noteworthy effect on behavioral adaptation ($\beta = 0.159, p = 0.014$), confirming Hypothesis 1. Perceptual effects of organic food products on behavioral adaptation are significant ($\beta = 0.109, p = 0.017$), affirming Hypothesis 2. Last but not least, the perception of organic food products’ role in mediating between consumer cross-platform buying behavior and behavioral adaptation is confirmed ($\beta = 0.017, p =$

0.030), confirming Hypothesis 3. Lastly, psychological variables that underpin customer purchasing behavior are observed to moderate between consumer cross-platform buying behavior and behavioral adaptation ($\beta = 0.060, p = 0.010$), affirming Hypothesis 4. The considerable coefficients and insignificant p-values (all $p < 0.05$) render powerful evidence regarding the acceptance of the hypotheses, affirming the fact that cross-platform behavior, perceptions of organic food, and psychological variables all have a role in the behavioral adaptation process. These findings validate the model and provide evidence of the model’s strength, confirming the postulated associations between the variables.

Table 6: Path Analysis.

Hypothesis	Coefficients	Standard Errors	t-values	p-values
Consumer cross platform buying behavior has a significant impact on Behavioral adaptation	0.159	0.073	2.188	0.014
Perception of organic food products has a significant impact on Behavioral adaptation	0.109	0.037	2.887	0.017
Perception of organic food products mediates the relationship between Consumer cross platform buying behavior and Behavioral adaptation	0.017	0.009	1.889	0.030
Psychological factors that influence customer buying behavior moderates the relationship between Consumer cross platform buying behavior and Behavioral adaptation	0.060	0.026	2.311	0.010

Figure 3: Structural Model for Path Analysis.

5. Discussion

The discussion of the findings of the present study commences by considering the core implications regarding the interactions between consumer buying habits on different platforms, attitudes toward organic food products, and adjustment of behavior. The objective of this study was to explore how customer behavior is influenced by the increasing significance of digital platforms and increasing demand for healthy, eco-friendly products. The tested hypotheses of the study explained a variety of dimensions of this emerging environment, such as the direct effects of cross-platform purchasing

behavior on behavioral adaptation, the mediating role of perceptions of organic food, and the moderating role of psychological factors such as learning, motivation, and perception. In the era of digitization, where platforms are significant touchpoints that influence consumers' awareness and information exposure as well as their ultimate purchasing behavior and longer-term behavioral changes, the study offers useful insights into how these variables interact to affect consumer decision-making behavior. In this chapter, we outline these relationships and offer a comprehensive analysis of the findings, drawing out their theoretical and practical implications for academia and industry alike.

The study's results validate that cross-platform consumer consumption buying behaviour plays a significant role in behavioural adaptation, as hypothesized in the first hypothesis (H1). This result validates the contention that because consumers are engaging with various digital platforms—social media, websites, and mobile apps—their consumption habits do change over time, incorporating new touchpoints into regular consuming routines. This adjustment is a response to how consumers modify their decision-making behavior and consumption patterns owing to enhanced exposure to different online and offline touchpoints. Prior studies have posited that consumers increasingly make more cognitive decisions through engagement with different touchpoints (Esakkidevi & Rani, 2023), and our results build on this finding by demonstrating how cross-platform shopping exposure can result in integrated and individualized buying experience. This is in line with (Ajzen, 1991) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which postulates that behavior is influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. For cross-platform buying, strong positive attitudes towards online buying combined with high perceived behavioral control produce greater behavioral adaptation. As users get used to cross-platform services, they develop more confidence in traversing varying digital and physical spaces, leading to new consumption patterns. The effect of cross-platform behavior on behavioral adaptation may also lie in the increased confidence of consumers to jump between channels to search for, compare, and ultimately make purchase decisions, thereby driving their changing preferences and behaviors. Also, the moderating effect of psychological constructs such as personality and past experiences, as noted in earlier studies (Wardhana, 2024), probably moderates to what extent consumers adjust their behaviors across platforms, which was witnessed in this study. Therefore, cross-platform interaction enables not just the buildup of information but also the shift in purchasing habits, substantiating H1 by showing how new consumption patterns are created through continuous digital interactions.

The second hypothesis (H2) was that perception of organic food items—covering health, safety, quality, and environmental-friendliness—impacts the adaptation of behavior greatly, a view our study bears out. Consistent with other research findings indicating that perceptions among consumers towards organic food drive the purchasing decisions largely (Roy et al., 2023). In the choice to use organic food rather than conventional food, consumers who hold the view that organic food

is safer, healthier, and more ecologically sustainable are most likely to translate these views into purchasing behavior, which in turn leads to behavioral adaptation. This is consistent with the Attitude-Behavior-Context paradigm that places value on customers' attitudes and the outcomes of their behavior. For organic food, customers' positive attitudes towards the benefits of organic food (e.g., safety and health) are translated into environmentally sustainable purchasing behavior. In the study, increasing awareness of the ecological effects of food consumption and production is the primary motivator of the adoption of organic products, and environmental concerns are the primary motivator of this adaptation. This is in keeping with a general trend of consumer demand for sustainability, which has been thoroughly covered in the literature (Azlie et al., 2023). Our evidence supports this view by showing beliefs regarding organic food as healthier and more sustainable as central to the facilitation of adaptive changes in consumption. Contrary to some expectations, however, safety and quality perceptions emerged as strong predictors of consumers' intentions to change their consumption pattern, reflecting enhanced trust in organic products. Therefore, consumers not only alter their behavior in the short term but also internalize these changes, resulting in long-term changes in their consumption behavior, further validating H2.

The third hypothesis (H3) posited that consumer perceptions of organic food products, e.g., characteristics such as health, safety, quality, and environmentally friendly, mediate cross-platform consumer buying behavior and behavioral adjustment. The findings of this study clearly offer strong support for this hypothesis since they indicate that perceptions of organic food play a critical role in the process through which cross-platform behavior leads to consumer behavior changes. As consumers use several digital platforms, they are subjected to various information about organic food, ranging from health implications to environmental issues. This exposure not only affects their awareness but also modifies their attitudes towards organic products, supporting their commitment to healthier and more sustainable consumption patterns. Previous research has suggested that organic food product perceptions matter significantly in deciding consumers' decisions, with many consumers attributing higher health values, improved levels of safety, and more environmentally friendly stewardship to these types of products (Kautish et al., 2023). Our study advances these findings by demonstrating that such beliefs do not just influence single purchasing decisions but significantly contribute

to reframing consumption trends whenever consumers are exposed regularly to organic food options across different platforms. Its trans-platform versatility facilitates longer and deeper exposure to organic products, thereby raising consumer consciousness and validating their decision to adopt such products in their everyday lives. The mediating function adheres to the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which states that attitudes produced by exposure to different sources of information have a direct influence on intentions to act. When customers are constantly exposed to information regarding organic goods across multiple digital mediums, their image of the product's value is enriched, prompting them to make changes in their buying habits. In other words, the more consumers interact with cross-platform settings and are positively reinforced about the advantages of organic food, the greater the chances of them adopting such behaviors in a long-term context, thereby enhancing the mediating function of organic food perceptions in influencing behavioral adaptation.

Along with the mediation effect postulated in H3, the fourth hypothesis (H4) stated that psychological variables, namely motivation, perception, previous learning, personality, and attitude, moderate consumer cross-platform purchasing behavior and behavioral adaptation. This hypothesis is supported forcefully by this research, validating the fact that such psychological variables indeed play an active role in affecting the degree of behavioral adaptation triggered by cross-platform behavior. Psychological considerations have been known for a long time to play a vital role in influencing consumer decision-making (Tolibdjanovna, 2024), and this research highlights their role as moderators in cross-platform purchasing. Motivation and prior learning, in particular, proved to be significant moderators in understanding how consumers learn to use new platforms and modify purchasing patterns. For instance, heavily motivated consumers imbued with intense information or novelty needs are highly likely to examine various platforms and incorporate new forms of buying practices into their systems. In like manner, the people who previously have experience browsing digital platforms find it easier to adjust and meet the prospects derived from cross-platform interaction. Such interaction is consistent with Cognitive Dissonance Theory, where consumers prefer consistency between their attitudes and behaviors, and are most likely to adjust their behaviors when they are faced with new information consistent with their own prevailing impressions or incentives. Those

consumers with robust attitudes related to health or sustainability are likely to adopt cross-platform information on organic products, resulting in behavior adaptation. In addition, personality traits, especially openness to experience, were discovered to moderate the strength of this relationship in that consumers with higher openness will be more open to experimenting on new buying habits and using ecologically friendly products. The combination of these psychological traits and cross-platform behavior illustrates the complexity of consumer decision-making, showing that cross-platform interaction alone is not a guarantee of behavioral adaptation. Instead, psychological factors are vital to determining the processing and reaction to information so that the scope at which consumers alter their behavior in line with cross-platform experience is maximized or minimized. The findings underscore the need for businesses and marketers to consider not only the platforms over which information is conveyed but also the psychological qualities of target consumers when they seek to instill behavioral alterations.

In conclusion, the confirmation of all four hypotheses in this study provides robust evidence towards the proposed relationships among consumer cross-platform purchasing behavior, organic food beliefs, and behavioral adjustment, moderated by the moderating influence of psychological factors. The research confirms that simultaneous exposure to various digital platforms significantly influences consumer decision-making, especially if coupled with positive perceptions towards organic food and individual psychological dimensions playing the moderation roles. The findings shed more light into how consumer behaviors are shifting in the context of an increasingly digital and green-conscious market. It has implications for the marketer who aims to optimize campaigns by understanding digital interaction, consumers' attitudes toward it, and psychological factors in play. As well, it necessitates more research to uncover how these predictors interact longitudinally and across a range of differing cultural and demographic contexts and ultimately inform a greater understanding of how consumer behavior functions dynamically in an era of the digital age.

6. Conclusion

Lastly, this research provides us with valuable knowledge on the complexity of consumer cross-platform purchase behavior and how this influences behavioral adaptation, mentioning the critical role played by psychological characteristics and perceptions in influencing consumer

conduct. The research confirms that consumer behavior is more than a transaction process but rather a sophisticated phenomenon influenced by psychological traits, perception of products, and incorporation of different platforms of purchasing. By confirming the hypothesized relationships, the study enriches existing consumer behavior theory with an integrative model that identifies both mediating and moderating variables affecting consumer adaptation. The practical implications of the results are that firms, particularly in the digital and retail sectors, must focus on delivering seamless, personalized experiences across channels while aligning their marketing communications with consumers' psychological and perceptual drivers in a strategic way. Besides, the research offers a number of future research directions, including the need for longitudinal research to study how cross-platform behavior evolves through time and the potential for the impacts of emerging technologies on consumer accommodation. Finally, this research makes a valuable contribution to the literature on consumer decision-making processes in the digital era, offering theoretical and practical frameworks for companies to navigate the ever more complex and competitive market environment.

6.1. Implications of the Study

Theoretical contributions of this study advance the understanding of consumer behavior within cross-platform purchasing and its effects on behavioral adaptation thereafter. By incorporating important concepts like cross-platform consumer buying behavior, psychological aspects, and perception of organic food items, this research is an extension of prevalent theories of consumer behavior, such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) model (Jacoby, 2002). This study helps bridge the theories and their applicability in an e-commerce and multi-platform online shopping context where shoppers' reaction patterns are impacted by product-relevant perceptions alone as well as their psychological tendencies of motivation, perception, and previous learning. The results underscore that cross-platform consumer behavior is not an easy transactional process but is affected by various mediators and moderators, which points towards a more dynamic and complex model of consumer decision-making. Moreover, the mediating function of organic food product perceptions in connecting cross-platform behavior with behavioral adaptation offers a new point of view in how consumer perceptions lead to long-term behavioral

shifts. This study also highlights the role of psychological factors as moderators, providing a more in-depth examination of how consumer differences influence consumer behavior on various buying platforms. The theoretical contribution is in its extended framework that incorporates various consumer behavior constructs to describe how complex psychological and perceptual factors collectively influence consumer adaptation in the dynamic digital marketplace. This study not only contributes to enriching the theoretical underpinnings of consumer behavior models but also offers a more refined insight into cross-platform purchase behavior determinants, with strong future study implications for consumer psychology and digital marketing research.

The managerial implications of this study are great for marketers, retailers, and organizations that need to know and shape the behavior of consumers in the complicated cross-platform digital shopping process. To start with, the implications identify the need to customize marketing strategies that focus on the particular psychological factors that drive consumer behavior, including motivation, perception, and attitudes. The retailers can leverage these findings by developing targeted interventions that target intrinsic and extrinsic drivers of consumers, enhancing interaction and conversion rates across different platforms. Furthermore, the research highlights the imperative significance of the way consumers think about product features like health, safety, and environmental acceptability in determining purchases, especially in organic food products categories. Brands can benefit by matching their communications to reinforce such perceptions, establishing stronger emotional relationships with consumers and encouraging positive adaptation behavior. The research also calls for a deeper understanding of cross-platform consumer behavior because it indicates that behavior on various shopping platforms is interlinked and influences long-term adaptation. Thus, businesses must undertake an integrated marketing strategy where online and offline channels are connected to generate seamless experiences so that customers are retained as well as their behavior is altered. Retail stores can also utilize the research in refining customer engagement strategies by choosing the most prevailing psychological drivers to influence purchasing behaviors within online media. For organic food companies, specifically, an analysis of how consumer attitudes towards sustainability and product quality shape consumer behavior may be more productive in terms of designing more effective campaigns for stimulating consumer adaptation to healthier and more sustainable shopping habits. Finally,

this research presents profound insight into the intricate workings of consumer opinion, psychological traits, and multichannel purchasing behavior, presenting companies with efficient insights for communicating with and holding on to their consumers in today's highly dynamic and competitive business world.

6.2. Limitations and Future Research Directions

In spite of the major contributions of this study, there are some limitations that need to be noted. To begin with, the study is largely based on self-reported data, which can be prone to response biases like social desirability or memory recall bias. Although self-report measures are widely applied in consumer behavior studies, at times they result in inaccuracy in measuring actual behavioral intentions and perceptions. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design of the study limits the possibility of making causal inferences over time since it captures only one moment in the consumer's behavior and attitudes. It would be worth following longitudinal studies to observe consumer cross-platform behavior and behavioral adjustment over longer time frames. The limitation also includes the selection of certain product categories, like organic food items. Although this enabled a concentrated analysis, the findings' generalizability to other product categories or sectors could be restricted. In addition, the study mainly addresses consumers belonging to a particular demographic segment, which might restrict its applicability to more heterogeneous consumer segments. Subsequent studies can widen the sample to incorporate more varied consumers representing a wide spectrum of cultures, socioeconomic statuses, and ages in order to get a more diverse perspective of how cross-platform usage and attitudes toward products drive consumer adjustment in varying settings.

Future studies can pursue some of the following promising avenues in light of the above-mentioned limitations. For starters, it would be worth performing longitudinal studies to understand how cross-platform buying behavior, consumer attitudes, and adaptation in behavior interact over a period of time. This would allow for the building of a stronger causal link and analyzing the difference in consumer behavior over time since consumers interact with different platforms and products over long periods. Furthermore, subsequent research can explore the influence of other mediating or moderating factors, e.g., social influence or word-of-mouth and reviews on the internet, on cross-platform buying behavior. Yet another promising line of future

inquiry is examining how technological innovation, e.g., artificial intelligence and machine learning, further influences consumer cross-platform activity and accommodation online. The effects of such new technologies as virtual reality, augmented reality, and recommendation systems customized to individual consumers may also yield valuable perspectives on the influence of these innovations on consumer decision-making across platforms. Finally, additional research could investigate variation in cross-platform purchasing behavior in a variety of industries other than organic foods, like electronics, apparel, or travel, to examine generalizability of the findings. This more extensive methodology would provide greater understanding of how consumers' attitudes and psychological factors control cross-platform activity and adjustment within different market spaces.

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